

How do help-seeking and help-abuse affect learning achievement in an interactive learning environment?

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ABSTRACT

Students' help-seeking behavior plays a central role in successful learning with interactive learning environments (ILEs), such as intelligent tutoring systems that provide on-demand help, including step-by-step hints or strategic help for solving mathematics problems. However, learners can also abuse the help offered when trying to successfully complete an ILE by using the hints provided primarily to find the required solution with as little effort as possible, rather than using the hints to support their learning efforts. This type of help abuse by learners undermines the purpose of an ILE. The present study investigated the extent to which self-reported help-abuse of 322 student teachers mediates the effect of observed help-seeking on learning number conversion in an ILE. Further, we examined the moderating effects of prior knowledge and academic self-concept in mathematics (MSC) on the effects of help-seeking and help-abuse on learning. The results showed that increased help-seeking had a significant negative impact on learning achievement. However, this could only be observed for the use of step-by-step hints, but not for the use of strategic help. The extent of self-reported help-abuse largely mediated the negative influence of observed help-seeking on learning achievement. The study indicates that step-by-step hints in ILEs could be faded out in the learning process and that more emphasis should be placed on strategic help that encourages self-explanations.

1. Introduction

Many interactive learning environments (ILEs), such as intelligent tutoring systems, offer immediate help when needed in the form of content-related hints and feedback on solution steps if a learner has difficulty achieving a learning goal or solving a problem [51],[57]. Within this interaction between the ILE and learner [30], students' help-seeking behaviors play a central role in successful learning [4,5,30,51,52]. Help-seeking is an important aspect of self-regulated learning [27,36], in general and especially in ILEs where learners have to decide for themselves when they need help and what kind of help they need [18].

Help is a type of scaffolding that facilitates students' ability to solve current problems. Help-seeking assists students in dealing with complex concepts that they either do not understand or feel they cannot understand on their own [17,29]. Studies on help-seeking focus on whether students use the scaffolding of help to solve problems, learn from help, and become able to solve problems without help [18]. However, learners can also abuse the help offered when trying to successfully

complete an ILE by using the hints provided primarily to find the required solution with as little effort as possible, rather than using the hints to support their learning efforts.

As school learning and active participation in society become increasingly digitalized activities, it is vital to develop a solid understanding of why, when, and how people are able to access help and to have the knowledge needed to provide accessible and functional help [7,56]. However, there are still gaps—and sometimes contradictory findings—within the literature regarding the effects, influencing factors, and conditions of help-seeking in ILEs [39,58].

The objective of this study is to expand the body of evidence regarding the impact of help-seeking on learning by investigating how and under what conditions help-seeking has a positive impact on learning achievement for student teachers in tertiary education working within an ILE to learn number conversion between decimal and non-decimal number systems. The analyses address the extent to which deliberate, self-reported help-abuse mediates the effect of help-seeking on learning observed in the ILE. In addition, the study investigates the moderating effects of prior knowledge and academic self-concept on the

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impacts of help-seeking and help-abuse on learning.

2. Background and hypotheses

2.1. Help-seeking

Help-seeking is an achievement behavior that involves the search for and use of strategies to achieve success [6]. Many researchers assume that help-seeking consists of five steps [5,34,36]: (1) become aware of the need for help, (2) decide to seek help, (3) identify potential helper(s), (4) use strategies to elicit help, and (5) evaluate a help-seeking episode. In the final steps, which are particularly important for learning, learners need to integrate new information with their existing knowledge and evaluate the quality of the help they received. If the help was not useful, they must request further help [49]. In some ILEs, learners can also decide whether they want to work on extra exercises to consolidate their knowledge or receive further help. These considerations characterize help-seeking as an intentional process that requires personal effort, is tailored to the current problem-solving ability, and is guided by learners' abilities and goals [5,26,50].

Razzaq and Hefferman [40] report that on-demand hints lead to greater learning gains than automatic hints in the context of middle school math. Further studies also show that providing on-demand help leads to better learning [5,41]. However, the effectiveness of help-seeking behavior varies widely across studies; authors report inconsistent (i.e., positive and negative) correlations between help-seeking and learning [4,13,30]. Some authors report that the use of help is typically associated with students who are struggling and, often, not making substantial progress in their learning, which may explain some of the negative association between help-seeking and learning [1, 4]. Karumbaiah et al. [28] report that the relationship between help-seeking and math performance varied widely, with correlations within schools ranging from -0.39 to 0.40 . The authors conclude that, despite extensive research, the effectiveness of help-seeking remains an open question and the relationship between help-seeking and learning is complicated [28].

2.2. Help-Abuse

Baker et al. [10] mention several studies in which learners attempted to succeed in an ILE by exploiting its properties rather than by learning the material and trying to use their knowledge to produce a correct answer. Baker et al. [10] refer to this behavior as "gaming the system." Alevén et al. [3] describe the excessive use of help as a type of maladaptive help-seeking behavior called "help abuse." The current study also uses the term "help-abuse" to refer to a help-seeking behavior that is primarily intended to obtain results while not supporting efforts to learn, thus contradicting the purpose of a learning environment.

Similarly, a distinction is made between executive help-seeking and instrumental help-seeking [27]. The goal of executive help-seeking is to reduce the cost of completing a task, such as by asking others for the answer to a problem. In contrast, the goal of instrumental help-seeking is to obtain the minimum amount of support needed to independently complete a task. Learning takes place primarily when the learner wants to understand the problem and how to solve it, rather than when the learner simply wants to receive a solution to a given problem [38].

Many studies report that learners often do not use help systems in ILEs appropriately and that, as a consequence, increased help-seeking is not always beneficial for learning [1,4,5,50]. Several studies report that help-abuse is ineffective, but instrumental help-seeking is effective for learning [5,18,37,54].

These findings suggest that the type of help-seeking, especially the extent of help-abuse, exhibited deliberately and intentionally by a learner has a decisive influence on the extent to which increased help-seeking may have a positive impact on learning. Thus, hypothesis 1 is as follows: help-abuse mediates the effect of help-seeking on learning

achievement.

2.3. Prior knowledge

Statements and findings on the relationship between prior knowledge and help-seeking are inconsistent. On the one hand, increased help-seeking is seen as a sign of students who are struggling [1,4]. This may indicate a negative association between prior knowledge and help-seeking or, as Dong et al. [20] observe, no significant effect of prior knowledge on help-seeking. On the other hand, studies report positive relationships between prior knowledge and help-seeking [5,45], which are attributed to the fact that a higher level of prior knowledge increases one's ability to assess the need for help [18]. Given this inconsistency, existing findings do not suggest a directional effect of prior knowledge on the extent of help-seeking.

Other studies investigate the extent to which prior knowledge moderates the relationship between help-seeking and learning. Wood and Wood [57] report that low-knowledge learners performed significantly better when they had a help-seeking tendency, but that this was not the case for higher-knowledge learners. This aligns with the findings of Renkl [41], which also suggest that learners who do not have a high level of prior knowledge achieve greater learning progress if they more frequently use help [5]. Beal et al. [12] also report that students with low mathematics achievement were most likely to engage in appropriate help-seeking. In line with these studies, hypothesis 2 is as follows: prior knowledge moderates the relationship between help-seeking and learning achievement, and learners with less prior knowledge benefit more from help-seeking than learners with higher prior knowledge.

2.4. Academic self-concept in mathematics

Academic self-concept indicates self-perceived ability within a particular academic area [16], for example in mathematics. It comprises not only a self-evaluative/cognitive dimension, but also an affective/-motivational dimension and affects students' motivation, emotion and achievement [22]. The self-concept can be seen as the basis for motivated behavior, as it gives rise to possible selves that create the motivation for behavior [21,23]. Mathematical self-concept (MSC) refers to a person's perception or belief about their ability to do well in math or to learn math [43]. MSC is known to predict mathematics performance [55] and achievement [32].

Newman [35] proposed that the decision to seek help is filtered through a motivational-affective system, including the self-concept. Studies report that positive self-concept is associated with a desire to remedy failure [19] and help-seeking [48]. Ryan and Pintrich [44] find no significant relationship between academic self-concept and adaptive help-seeking but a negative significant relationship between self-concept and avoidance of help-seeking. Beal et al. [12] report that students with low MSC were most likely to engage in inappropriate guessing behavior, but that there was no significant relationship between MSC and adaptive help-seeking. Karumbaiah et al. [28] report that correlations between help-seeking and MSC within schools showed a relatively wide range (-0.27 – 0.30). We found no studies investigating the potential moderating effects of MSC on the impact of help-seeking on achievement. Given the current state of research, we do not formulate a hypothesis regarding the possible effects of the MSC on help-seeking or its contribution to achievement.

3. Methods

3.1. The present study

The causal relationships described or assumed in the theoretical background are illustrated in Fig. 1 to coherently explain the research questions of this study. In addition to help-seeking, the processing of extra exercises is included as a variable. In line with the five steps that

Fig. 1. Effect model.

are assumed to take place in help-seeking [5,34,36], in the examined ILE, learners can voluntarily decide to work on extra exercises. At the center of the effect model (Fig. 1) is the mediation effect to be investigated, namely, the extent to which help-abuse mediates the effect of help-seeking on learning achievement (see hypothesis 1).

3.1.1. Explanation of learning achievement in an ILE

The first two research questions, including the testing of hypothesis 1, are intended to shed light on the sometimes contradictory results of research comparing help-seeking behavior and student performance or learning. The questions are as follows:

RQ1: How do help-seeking, working on extra exercises, and help-abuse contribute to learning achievement?

RQ2: To what extent does help-abuse mediate the effect of help-seeking on achievement?

3.1.2. Explanation of learning behavior in an ILE

Research question 3 is exploratory given the inconsistent state of research and allows us to better understand how learners' behavior is influenced by their abilities and their perceptions of those abilities:

RQ3: To what extent can help-seeking, the use of extra exercises, and help-abuse be explained by prior knowledge and MSC?

Moderating Effects on Learning

Research questions 4 and 5, including the testing of hypothesis 2, address the moderating effects of prior knowledge and MSC on the relationships between learning behavior in an ILE and learning achievement. The questions are as follows:

RQ4: To what extent does prior knowledge moderate the contributions of help-seeking, working on extra exercises, and help-abuse to achievement?

RQ5: To what extent does MSC moderate the contributions of help-seeking, working on extra exercises, and help-abuse to achievement?

3.2. Participants and procedure

A total of 322 first-year student teachers (210 female, 85 male, 27 other/missing; mean age: 22.7 years) intending to teach in primary school (grades 1–6) used an ILE (Cognitive Tutor Authoring Tools [CTAT] 4.2.0; [3]) to learn how to convert numbers between decimal and non-decimal place value systems. Anonymous work in the ILE was part of a learning assignment in a mathematics education module. The students worked independently with the ILE without any further human support (mean duration: 40.4 min, SD = 23.1 min). Before (prior knowledge, MSC) and after (post-test knowledge, help-abuse) working

with the ILE, the student teachers voluntarily completed questionnaires and tests in the software Survalyzer. The questionnaires and tests were anonymously linked to learning behavior (help-seeking, extra exercises) in the ILE.

In the ILE of the present study, the principles of the place value system for the base number 10 are explained and then gradually transferred to place value systems for the base numbers 3 and 2 with a focus on number conversion. The accompanying and illustrative learning tasks provide automated feedback on the correctness of answers for the learning tasks and offer distinguishable kinds [14,26,59] of on-demand help:

Hints for step-by-step solutions provided learners with a series of hints that build on each other and gradually become more concrete. For example, first, hints provide information on previously explained and task-relevant concepts, followed by general and then specific suggestions for a helpful procedure for the current step of the solution. Next, a hint will provide the calculation that is helpful at this point. Finally, the solution will be shown.

Procedural strategic help included blank formulas for a specific solution path. This help offered structured solution terms in which the meanings of place values were shown in the decimal system. A procedure for converting a number from the decimal system to another place value system, or vice versa, was explained previously in the ILE. In the help offered, the digits for searched numbers were left blank. For example, the structured term " $_ \cdot 243_{10} + _ \cdot 81_{10} + _ \cdot 27_{10} + _ \cdot 9_{10} + _ \cdot 3_{10} + _ \cdot 1_{10} = _$ " was offered for the task "Please convert the number 1021_3 into the decimal system" (translated from German). The equally structured term " $_ \cdot 243_{10} + _ \cdot 81_{10} + _ \cdot 27_{10} + _ \cdot 9_{10} + _ \cdot 3_{10} + _ \cdot 1 = 9_{10}$ " was offered for the task "Please convert the number 9_{10} into the base 3 system." Subscript numbers denote the base of a place value system. Further hints for step-by-step solutions were offered to help student teachers calculate numbers to fill the blanks.

Blank **place-value tables as conceptual strategic help** illustrated the meaning of the place values in non-decimal place value systems. This help contains conceptual information that can also be used to structure the path to a solution. Further hints for step-by-step solutions were offered to help student teachers calculate the missing numbers in blank cells of a place value table.

Optional **extra exercises** were also offered. In these exercises, all the types of help described above could be requested.

The conversion of natural numbers between decimal and non-decimal place value systems is a part of mathematics teacher education at many universities. This learning objective is intended, among other things, to foster a better understanding of the decimal place value system [31]. This learning context is suitable for analyzing the effectiveness of help-seeking and help-abuse; solving number conversion tasks is challenging for many student teachers, as it is based on procedural and conceptual knowledge components [47].

3.3. Measures

Prior knowledge was measured with 5 items (reliability = 0.795), and post-test knowledge was measured with 9 items (reliability = 0.924) in order to assess learning achievement. Items with numbers from place value systems other than 2 and 3, which were covered in the ILE, also required the ability to transfer lessons learned to other place value systems (4, 5, 7, 9, and 16).

The process variables observed in the log data from the ILE for help-seeking (use of hints, procedural strategic help, and conceptual strategic help) and extra exercises included the learning behavior (frequencies, e. g. of help requests) of student teachers in ten task fields, which consisted of several individual tasks.

As explained in the theoretical background, help-abuse is a deliberate and intentional learning behavior. Learners can therefore provide retrospective information about this type of user behavior. Help-abuse was measured with 5 items (reliability = 0.766) in the post-test (example items: “I playfully clicked through the hints until the correct answer I was looking for was given,” “The help available prevented me from looking for a solution myself,” and after recoding from disapproval to approval and vice versa “I usually tried to find the solution myself before seeking help”).

MSC was measured with 9 items (reliability = 0.888) in the pre-test (example items: “I enjoy mathematics,” “I am good at math,” and “In math, I like to work out solutions myself, even if it’s challenging”).

3.4. Analysis

A structural equation model (SEM) operationalized the relationships between variables from the effect model (Fig. 1) with AMOS software [8]. Few missing data (about 2 %) were imputed with NORM software (version 2.03) [46], as AMOS does not allow missing data during the estimation of p-values for total direct and indirect effects [15] in a SEM. Due to the verified one-dimensionality of the scales (see the reliabilities in 3.3) and the fact that we use the SEM to analyze relationships between scales and not the loadings of the individual items, in scales with >3 individual items, thematically similar items were combined into aggregated items [11,25]. This resulted in at least three manifest indicator items (all standardized factor loadings > 0.58) per latent variable (see ellipses in Fig. 1) in the final SEM with good model fit (number of parameters = 62, discrepancy = 102, degrees of freedom = 90, CFI [comparative fit index] = 0.994, RMSEA [root mean square error of approximation] = 0.020). For the moderator analyses, we formed two groups with a median split in terms of prior knowledge and MSC so that the standardized beta weights in the SEM could be compared between the two groups.

Table 1
Direct and Total Effects Regarding Learning Achievement and Learning Behavior.

Predictors	Criterion				Total effects (direct + indirect effects)		
	Help-seeking	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test
	β						
	(p-value)						
Pre-test	-0.130 (0.064)	-0.004 (0.945)	-0.030 (0.669)	.223 (<0.001)	-0.020 (0.747)	-0.073 (0.269)	.270 (<0.001)
MSC	-0.240 (<0.001)	0 (0.997)	-0.127 (0.070)	.048 (0.405)	-0.028 (0.584)	-0.209 (0.002)	.167 (0.003)
Help-seeking		.119 (0.078)	.361 (<0.001)	-0.112 (0.106)	.119 (0.084)	.340 (<0.001)	-0.258 (0.001)
Extra exercises			-0.174 (0.006)	.064 (0.224)		-0.174 (0.002)	.143 (<0.001)
Help-abuse				-0.452 (<0.001)			-0.452 (<0.001)

4. Results

The learning achievement of all participants was characterized by a large effect size: $d = 0.79$ ($p < .001$, T-test). This calculation is based on five items, which were identical in the pre-test (mean: 1.15; SD: 1.50) and post-test (mean: 2.81; SD: 1.89). Thus, the log-data and self-reports collected in this ILE are suitable for investigating the effects and conditioning factors of learning behavior.

4.1. Explanation of learning achievement and learning behavior in the ILE

The data in Table 1 provide answers to RQ1 and RQ3 and are used for the mediator analysis performed to answer RQ2.

4.1.1. Effects on learning achievement (RQ1)

Neither MSC, help-seeking, nor working on extra exercises had a significant direct effect on learning achievement. In contrast, self-reported help-abuse had a clearly negative direct effect on learning achievement at the time of the post-test.

However, higher MSC had a positive total effect on achievement when considering the total (direct and indirect) effects of MSC on achievement via help-seeking, extra exercises, and help-abuse (see the paths in Fig. 1). The total effect of working on extra exercises on achievement was also positive and significant. The total effect of help-seeking on achievement via extra exercises and help-abuse was clearly negative and significant. These results already illustrate that the effects of help-seeking, extra exercises and MSC on learning achievement are all mediated by the level of self-reported help-abuse.

Thus, all predictors in Fig. 1 significantly influence learning achievement and together can explain 36 % of its variance. The greatest negative effect is caused by help-abuse, followed by help-seeking. MSC and working on extra exercises have a slightly less strong, but positive, effect on learning achievement. This result clearly underlines the great importance of the quality of help-seeking for learning.

4.1.2. Effects on help-abuse (RQ3)

Neither prior knowledge nor MSC had a significant direct influence on help-abuse. However, higher MSC had a negative total effect on help-abuse when considering the total (direct and indirect) effects of MSC on help-abuse via help-seeking and extra exercises. Increased help-seeking was clearly associated with increased help-abuse, while increased work on extra exercises was associated with decreased help-abuse.

Increased help-abuse therefore occurs above all with increased help-seeking. Here, help-abuse is independent of prior knowledge, but is stimulated by a negative academic self-concept.

4.1.3. Effects on extra exercises (RQ3)

None of the predictors had a significant effect on whether learners engaged in extra exercises. However, there is a small and just non-significant tendency for increased help-seeking to be associated with increased use of extra exercises.

4.1.4. Effects on help-seeking (RQ3)

Higher MSC resulted in less help-seeking. This is in line with the operationalization of MSC, which also includes the self-reported preference to work out solutions oneself, even if it is challenging. The effect of prior knowledge on help-seeking, which tended to be negative, only just failed to reach the significance level. It can be summarized that help-seeking behavior is less influenced by prior knowledge, but is more clearly stimulated by a negative academic self-concept.

4.1.5. Mediator analysis (RQ2)

The following standardized beta weights (p-values) are relevant for answering RQ2: the direct effect of help-seeking on achievement (Table 1) was -0.112 ($p = .106$); the indirect effect of help-seeking on achievement via help-abuse (Fig. 1) was -0.146 (<0.001), and the total effect of help-seeking on achievement (Table 1) was -0.258 (0.001). Although the direct effect of help seeking on achievement is not significant, there was a negative total effect due to the significant negative indirect effect of help-seeking via help-abuse on achievement. Thus, the extent of help-abuse significantly mediates the negative effect of increased help-seeking on achievement by 57 % (indirect effect / total effect = $-0.146 / -0.258$). Thus, hypothesis 1 was confirmed.

4.1.6. How do the uses of the different types of help affect learning?

Although the factor loadings (-693 – 765) of the three types of help (see 3.2) make it clear that help-seeking can be modeled as a unidimensional construct (see Fig. 1), we separately analyzed the influences of the three types of help as manifest variables, instead of a common latent variable, on learning achievement in the SEM as part of a supplementary post-hoc analysis. It was found that only increased use of hints for step-by-step solutions (-0.272 ; $p < .001$) had a negative significant total effect on learning achievement. Neither the increased use of procedural strategic help (-0.070 ; $p = .314$) nor conceptual strategic help (0.065 ; $p = .344$) had significant effects.

Thus, when analyzing the effects of help-seeking behavior, a distinction should be made as to which types of help are offered and used. No negative influence on learning achievement was observed in this ILE with increased use of strategic help, only with increased use of hints for step-by-step solutions.

4.2. Moderating effects of prior knowledge on learning achievement and learning behavior

A median split regarding prior knowledge was performed. The 322 participants were divided into two groups: 168 (52.2 %) had no prior

knowledge and did not correctly solve any item in the pre-test, and 154 (47.8 %) had correctly solved 1–5 of the items. The data in Table 2 provide answers for RQ4.

4.2.1. Moderating effect of prior knowledge on total effects on achievement (RQ4)

MSC only had a significant effect on the post-test for learners with some or higher prior knowledge. No significant effect of MSC was found for learners with no prior knowledge. Accordingly, a higher academic self-concept was only beneficial for learning if it was accompanied by a higher level of prior knowledge.

The effects of help-seeking and help-abuse on the post-test were equally negative and significant in both groups, regardless of the level of prior knowledge. Despite the tendencies in the beta weights, the significance levels also show no moderating effect of prior knowledge on the total effects of both learning behavior variables (help seeking and help-abuse) on the post-test. A post-hoc analysis investigated whether there were moderating effects of prior knowledge on the direct effects of the learning behavior variables on achievement. All chi-square difference tests on the models with restricted parameters were not significant. Hence, prior knowledge did not moderate the relationship between help-seeking and learning achievement. Thus, hypothesis 2 was not confirmed.

4.2.2. Further moderating effects of prior knowledge

Higher MSC considerably reduced help-abuse in the group with higher prior knowledge, but not in the group without prior knowledge. Thus, a higher prior knowledge proves to be an important moderator for the overall favorable effect of a higher MSC on a reduction of help-abuse. A higher MSC only reduces help-abuse if it is accompanied by a higher level of prior knowledge.

Conversely, increased processing of extra exercises was associated with less help-abuse in the group without prior knowledge, but not in the group with higher prior knowledge. Thus, the tendency to work on extra tasks only indicates a low level of help-abuse in learners without prior knowledge.

Higher MSC led to decreased help-seeking in the group with higher prior knowledge, but not significantly in the group without prior knowledge. Accordingly, a higher MSC only reduces help-seeking if it is accompanied by a higher level of prior knowledge. In summary, it can be stated that the favorable influences of a positive academic self-concept on learning were only effective if they were also accompanied by a higher level of prior knowledge.

4.3. Moderating effects of academic self-concept on learning achievement and learning behavior

A median split regarding MSC (range: 1–4, median: 2.67) divided the 322 participants into two groups: 175 (54.3 %) had lower MSC and 147 (45.7 %) had higher MSC. The data in Table 3 provide answers for RQ5.

Table 2
Moderating effects of prior knowledge.

Predictors	Criterion (total effects)							
	No prior knowledge				Some or higher prior knowledge			
	Help-seeking β (p-value)	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test	Help-seeking	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test
MSC	-0.173 (0.084)	.013 (0.886)	-0.088 (0.390)	.123 (0.093)	-0.341 (0.001)	-0.055 (0.388)	-0.356 (<0.001)	.256 (0.004)
Help-seeking		.178 (0.074)	.289 (0.004)	-0.214 (0.035)		.061 (0.535)	.367 (0.003)	-0.367 (0.001)
Extra exercises			-0.255 (0.001)	.137 (0.016)			-0.100 (0.249)	.146 (0.038)
Help-abuse				-0.506 (0.001)				-0.389 (0.003)

Table 3
Moderating effects of academic self-concept in mathematics (MSC).

Predictors	Criterion (total effects)							
	Lower MSC				Higher MSC			
	Help-seeking β (p-value)	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test	Help-seeking	Extra exercises	Help-abuse	Post-test
Pre-test	-0.136 (0.098)	-0.067 (0.347)	-0.004 (0.998)	.218 (0.022)	-0.148 (0.109)	.038 (0.769)	-0.117 (0.068)	.353 (<0.001)
Help-seeking		.012 (0.907)	.381 (<0.001)	-0.343 (0.001)		.273 (0.001)	.307 (0.011)	-0.164 (0.011)
Extra exercises			-0.176 (0.022)	.186 (0.001)			-0.188 (0.010)	.058 (0.340)
Help-abuse				-0.320 (0.003)				-0.575 (0.001)

4.3.1. Moderating effect of MSC on total effects on achievement (RQ5)

Extra exercises had a positive effect on learning achievement in the group with lower MSC, but not in the group with higher MSC. No such moderating effect was found for prior knowledge: The results from Table 2 showed that learners with and without prior knowledge equally benefited from working on extra tasks. These extended results from Table 3 indicate that learners with lower MSC in particular used extra tasks in a way that was conducive to learning, regardless of their prior knowledge.

The effect size of the negative influence of help-abuse tended to be larger in the group with higher prior knowledge, while the effect size of the negative relationship between help-seeking and learning achievement was larger in the group with lower MSC. However, all these effects are significant in both groups. Thus, the results indicated no moderating effect of MSC on the effects of the two main learning behavior variables (help-seeking and help-abuse) on achievement.

4.3.2. Further moderating effects of MSC

Increased help-seeking was associated with the use of extra exercises in the group with higher MSC, but not in the group with lower MSC. Due to the experience of needing more help, the decision to work on more extra tasks is accordingly favored by the fact that a higher MSC is given at the same time.

The results thus indicate various influences of the academic self-concept on learning behavior in an ILE: On the one hand, a high MSC encourages the conclusion to work more on extra tasks due to increased help-seeking. On the other hand, working on extra tasks is primarily effective for learners with a lower MSC. An influence of the academic self-concept on learning behavior could thus be identified. However, the effects of academic self-concept on learning behavior are complex and require further investigation.

5. Discussion

5.1. How does the use of on-demand help affect learning?

The present study investigated the learning behavior of student teachers who used an ILE with on-demand help to learn number conversion. The findings showed that increased help-seeking had a clear negative influence on learning achievement. Unlike some prior studies have suggested [1,4], this is not because learners with less prior knowledge need more help and yet learn less than learners with more prior knowledge. In the present data set, there was no significant relationship between prior knowledge and the extent of help-seeking.

The mechanism by which increased help-seeking had a negative influence on learning achievement was investigated via a mediator analysis. This analysis showed that the extent of self-reported help-abuse was most responsible for this negative influence. Help-seeking was objectively determined from the recorded log files, but help-abuse was self-reported by the learners in retrospect by means of a questionnaire. As discussed in the theoretical background, studies have argued that help-seeking, and thus help-abuse, are intentional and deliberate actions [5, 26,35,50]. Thus, it makes sense to assess the extent of help-abuse via

self-reports. By combining observation logs and self-reports, the hypothesized mediating effect of help-seeking via help abuse on learning achievement could be operationalized, tested, and confirmed.

This study also investigated the extent to which the influences of help-seeking and help-abuse on learning achievement are impacted by personality characteristics, prior knowledge, and MSC. In contrast to some existing findings ([12,41]; [57]), we found no moderating effect of prior knowledge or MSC on the relationships between learning behavior (help-seeking and help-abuse) and learning achievement in the ILE. Consequently, the negative influence of increased help-seeking and, in particular, increased help-abuse is significant, large and consistent within the present sample.

From these and existing findings, further conclusions can be drawn about learning processes within an ILE with on-demand help. It is assumed that the interactivity encouraged by an ILE [5,9,30,33] is beneficial for learning. In previous pilot studies, extensive tests have been performed on the ILE used in this study, including an experimental design in which the expected learning benefits of the ILE were investigated in comparison to a non-interactive learning environment [60]. The comparison learning environment contained similar sequential explanations but no automatic feedback or on-demand help with learning tasks. No significant difference was found; both learning environments led to a comparably high learning gain. This suggests that interactivity is not primarily responsible for learning effectiveness in this ILE.

Another assumption is that stimulating self-explanations when learners engage with solved examples and accompanying explanations in an ILE are crucial for learning achievement [5,18,30,33,41,53]. The results of the current study are consistent with this assumption. Only increased use of hints for step-by-step solutions, and not increased use of procedural or conceptual strategic help, had a negative influence on learning success. The two types of strategic help [26] illustrated the basic principles of a place value system to help student teachers plan multi-step solutions for converting numbers between place value systems. These types of help require student teachers to link complex information and understand the illustrated principles, which is difficult to capture without accompanying self-explanations.

The current study contributes findings regarding the importance of academic self-concept for help-seeking behavior and learning in an ILE with on-demand help. For students with higher prior knowledge, higher MSC reduced help-seeking, which has been shown to have an overall detrimental effect on learning. In addition, for students with higher MSC, increased help-seeking resulted in increased voluntary completion of extra exercises. This is consistent with research findings and theories that view self-concept as the basis for motivated learning behavior [23, 36,48]. These results suggest that special attention should be given to students' academic self-concept so that they can successfully work in ILEs using on-demand help and extra exercises.

5.2. Limitations

This ILE was characterized by a relatively short average processing time of around 40 min. The findings therefore relate to short-term learning effects and learning processes. The extent to which the

duration of work in an ILE influences the observable relationships between learner behavior and learning achievement [5] remains a topic for further research.

5.3. Practical implications for ILE designs

There is a growing body of research on the learning effectiveness of ILEs that provide step-by-step hints combined with metacognitive prompts or prompts for self-explanation to improve the quality of help-seeking and processing [2,30,41,49,53]. The results of the present study indicate that the increased use of step-by-step hints was negatively associated with learning achievement, but the increased use of strategic help was not. Thus, it may be possible to improve the learning effectiveness of ILEs with on-demand help by fading out [42] step-by-step hints, but not strategic help.

From a broader perspective, the current study aims to contribute to the discussion regarding which kind of minimal help is best suited to support self-regulated learning in line with the zone of proximal development of an individual learner [5]. The concern to provide the best possible minimal help to learners with difficulties represents a key challenge for both ILEs and traditional classroom teaching [24,30]. Although the body of research about help-seeking in ILEs is growing [56], this challenge clearly deserves further attention.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andreas Schulz: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Johannes Voermanek:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- [1] Aleven V, Koedinger KR. Limitations of student control: do students know when they need help? In: Gauthier G, Frasson C, VanLehn K, editors. Lecture notes in computer science /edited by G.Goos, J. Hartmanis and J. van Leeuwen: Vol. 1839, Intelligent tutoring systems: 5th international conference, ITS 2000. Springer; 2000. p. 292–303. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45108-0_33.
- [2] Aleven V, McLaren B, Roll I, Koedinger K. Toward meta-cognitive tutoring: a model of help seeking with a cognitive tutor. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 2006;16(2):101–28. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/international-journal-of-artificial-intelligence-in-education/jai16-2-02>.
- [3] Aleven V, McLaren BM, Sewall J, Koedinger KR. The cognitive tutor authoring tools (CTAT): preliminary evaluation of efficiency gains. In: Mitsuru I, Ashley K, Chan T-W, editors. International Conference on Intelligent Tutoring Systems. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer; 2006. p. 61–70.
- [4] Aleven V, Roll I, McLaren BM, Koedinger KR. Help helps, but only so much: research on Help seeking with intelligent tutoring systems. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 2016;26(1):205–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-015-0089-1>.
- [5] Aleven V, Stahl E, Schworm S, Fischer F, Wallace R. Help seeking and Help design in interactive learning environments. *Rev Educ Res* 2003;73(3):277–320.
- [6] Ames R, Lau S. An attributional analysis of student help-seeking in academic settings. *J Educ Psychol* 1982;74(3):414–23. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.74.3.414>.
- [7] Amigud A, Hosseini S. Collaboration, collusion, and barter-cheating: an analysis of academic help-seeking behaviors. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education* 2024;49(3):392–407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2023.2259631>.
- [8] Arbuckle, J. (2012). *IBM SPSS Amos 21 user's guide*.
- [9] [Beverly Park][Carole R.] Arroyo I, Beck JE, Woolf BP, Beal CR, Schultz K. Macro-adapting Animalwatch to gender and cognitive differences with respect to hint interactivity and symbolism. In: Gauthier G, Frasson C, VanLehn K, editors. Lecture notes in computer science /edited by G.Goos, J.Hartmanis and J. van Leeuwen: Vol. 1839, Intelligent tutoring systems: 5th international conference, ITS 2000. Springer; 2000. p. 574–83. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45108-0_61.
- [10] Baker RS, Koedinger KR, Corbett AT, Wagner AZ, Evenson S, Roll I, Naim M, Raspat J, Beck JE. Adapting to when students game an intelligent tutoring system. In: Ashley K, Chan T-W, Ikeda M, editors. Lecture notes in computer science: vol. 4053, intelligent tutoring systems. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag; 2006. p. 392–401. https://doi.org/10.1007/11774303_39.
- [11] G. A. Marcoulides & R. E. Schumacker (Eds.) Bandalos D, Finney S. Item parceling issues in structural equation modeling. G. A. Marcoulides & R. E. Schumacker (Eds.). In: Erlbaum L, editor. *New developments and techniques in structural equation modeling*; 2001. p. 269–96.
- [12] [C. R.] Beal CR, Qu L, Lee H. Mathematics motivation and achievement as predictors of high school students' guessing and help-seeking with instructional software. *J Comput Assist Learn* 2008;24(6):507–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2008.00288.x>.
- [13] Beck JE, Chang K, Mostow J, Corbett A. Does help help? Introducing the bayesian evaluation and Assessment methodology. In: Woolf BP, Aïmeur E, Nkambou R, Lajoie S, editors. *Lecture notes in computer science: Vol. 5091, Intelligent Tutoring Systems: 9th International Conference, ITS 2008, Montreal, Canada, June 23-27, 2008 Proceedings*. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag; 2008. p. 383–94. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69132-7_42.
- [14] Belland BR, Walker AE, Kim NJ, Lefler M. Synthesizing results from empirical research on computer-based scaffolding in STEM education: a meta-analysis. *Rev Educ Res* 2017;87(2):309–44. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654316670999>.
- [15] Bollen KA. Total, direct, and indirect effects in structural equation models. *Sociol Methodol* 1987;17:37. <https://doi.org/10.2307/271028>.
- [16] Bong M, Skaalvik EM. Academic self-concept and self-efficacy: how different are they really? *Educ Psychol Rev* 2003;15(1):1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021302408382>.
- [17] Butler R, Neuman O. Effects of task and ego achievement goals on help-seeking behaviors and attitudes. *J Educ Psychol* 1995;87(2):261–71. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.87.2.261>.
- [18] Chou C-Y, Lai KR, Chao P-Y, Tseng S-F, Liao T-Y. A negotiation-based adaptive learning system for regulating help-seeking behaviors. *Comput Educ* 2018;126: 115–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.010>.
- [19] Diener CI, Dweck CS. An analysis of learned helplessness: continuous changes in performance, strategy, and achievement cognitions following failure. *J Pers Soc Psychol* 1978;36(5):451–62. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.36.5.451>.
- [20] Dong A, Jong MS-Y, King RB. How does prior knowledge influence learning engagement? The mediating roles of cognitive load and help-seeking. *Front Psychol* 2020;11:591203. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.591203>.
- [21] Erdogan F, Sengul S. A study on the elementary school students' Mathematics self concept. *1877-0428 2014;152:596–601*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.249>.
- [22] Ferla J, Valcke M, Cai Y. Academic self-efficacy and academic self-concept: reconsidering structural relationships. *Learn Individ Differ* 2009;19(4):499–505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2009.05.004>.
- [23] Franken R. *Human motivation*. Brooks/Cole Publishing Co; 1994.
- [24] Gerard L, Matuk C, McElhaney K, Linn MC. Automated, adaptive guidance for K-12 education. *Educ Res Rev* 2015;15:41–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.04.001>.
- [25] Hall RJ, Snell AF, Foust MS. Item parceling strategies in SEM: investigating the subtle effects of unmodeled secondary constructs. *Organ Res Methods* 1999;2(3): 233–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442819923002>.
- [26] Hannafin M, Land S, Oliver K. *Open Learning Environments : foundations, methods, and models*. Instructional-design theories and models. Routledge; 2013. p. 115–40. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410603784-8>.
- [27] Karabenick S, Knapp J. Relationship of academic help seeking to the use of learning strategies and other instrumental achievement behavior in college students. *J Educ Psychol* 1991;83(2):221–30.
- [28] Karumbaiah S, Ocuppaugh J, Baker RS. Context matters: differing implications of motivation and help-seeking in educational technology. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 2022;32(3):685–724. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-021-00272-0>.
- [29] Kitsantas A, Chow A. College students' perceived threat and preference for seeking help in traditional, distributed, and distance learning environments. *Comput Educ* 2007;48(3):383–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2005.01.008>.
- [30] Koedinger KR, Aleven V. Exploring the assistance dilemma in experiments with cognitive tutors. *Educ Psychol Rev* 2007;19(3):239–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-007-9049-0>.
- [31] Krauthausen G. *Einführung in die mathematikdidaktik – grundschule* (4. aufl. 2018). *mathematik primarstufe und sekundarstufe i + ii*. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer; 2018. <http://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:bsz:31-epflicht-1537518>.
- [32] Marsh HW, Trautwein U, Lüdtke O, Köller O, Baumert J. Academic self-concept, interest, grades, and standardized test scores: reciprocal effects models of causal ordering. *Child Dev* 2005;76(2):397–416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2005.00853.x>.
- [33] Mayer RE, Dow GT, Mayer S. *Multimedia learning in an interactive self-explaining environment: what works in the design of agent-based microworlds?* *J Educ Psychol* 2003;95(4):806–12.
- [34] Nelson-Le Gall S. Help-seeking: an understudied problem-solving skill in children. *Developmental Review* 1981;1(3):224–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-2297\(81\)90019-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-2297(81)90019-8).
- [35] Newman R. Adaptive help seeking: a strategy of self-regulated learning. In: Schunk DH, Zimmerman BJ, editors. *Self-regulation of learning and performance*; 1994. p. 1–19. <https://api.taylorfrancis.com/content/chapters/edit/download?identifiername=doi&identifiervalue=10.4324/9780203763353-12&type=chapterpdf>.
- [36] Newman R. The motivational role of adaptive help seeking in self-regulated learning. In: Schunk DH, Zimmerman BJ, editors. *Motivation and self-regulated learning //Motivation and self-regulated learning*. Routledge; 2012. p. 315–37.

- <https://api.taylorfrancis.com/content/chapters/edit/download?identifiername=doi&identifiervalue=10.4324/9780203831076-13&type=chapterpdf>.
- [37] Puustinen M. Help-seeking behavior in a problem-solving situation: development of self-regulation. *European Journal of Psychology of Education* 1998;13(2): 271–82. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03173093>.
- [38] Puustinen M, Volckaert-Legrier O, Coquin D, Bernicot J. An analysis of students' spontaneous computer-mediated help seeking: a step toward the design of ecologically valid supporting tools. *Comput Educ* 2009;53(4):1040–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2008.10.003>.
- [39] Qayyum A. Student help-seeking attitudes and behaviors in a digital era. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 2018;15(1):1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-018-0100-7>.
- [40] Razaq L, Heffernan NT. Hints: is it better to give or wait to be asked? In: Alevin V, editor. *Lecture notes in computer science: 6094-6095, Intelligent tutoring systems: 10th international conference : proceedings*. Springer; 2010. p. 349–58. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-13388-6_39.
- [41] Renkl A. Worked-out examples: instructional explanations support learning by self-explanations. *Learn Instr* 2002;12(5):529–56. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752\(01\)00030-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752(01)00030-5).
- [42] Renkl A, Atkinson RK, Große CS. How fading worked solution steps works – A cognitive load perspective. *Instr Sci* 2004;32(1/2):59–82. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:TRUC.0000021815.74806.f6>.
- [43] Reyes LH. Affective variables and mathematics education. *Elem Sch J* 1984;84(5): 558–81. <https://doi.org/10.1086/461384>.
- [44] Ryan AM, Pintrich PR. "Should I ask for help?" the role of motivation and attitudes in adolescents' help seeking in math class. *J Educ Psychol* 1997;89(2):329–41. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-0663.89.2.329>.
- [45] Ryan AM, Shin H. Help-seeking tendencies during early adolescence: an examination of motivational correlates and consequences for achievement. *Learn Instr* 2011;21(2):247–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2010.07.003>.
- [46] Schafer JL, Graham JW. Missing data: our view of the state of the art. *Psychol Methods* 2002;7(2):147–77. <https://doi.org/10.1037//1082-989X.7.2.147>.
- [47] Schulz A. Assessing student teachers' procedural fluency and strategic competence in operating and mathematizing with natural and rational numbers. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education* 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-023-09590-7>. Advance online publication.
- [48] Skaalvik EM, Skaalvik S. School goal structure: associations with students' perceptions of their teachers as emotionally supportive, academic self-concept, intrinsic motivation, effort, and help seeking behavior. *Int J Educ Res* 2013;61: 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2013.03.007>.
- [49] Stahl E, Bromme R. Not everybody needs help to seek help: surprising effects of metacognitive instructions to foster help-seeking in an online-learning environment. *Comput Educ* 2009;53(4):1020–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2008.10.004>.
- [50] Vaessen BE, Prins FJ, Jeuring J. University students' achievement goals and help-seeking strategies in an intelligent tutoring system. *Comput Educ* 2014;72: 196–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.11.001>.
- [51] van Lehn K. The behavior of tutoring systems. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 2006;16(3): 227–65. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/international-journal-of-artificial-intelligence-in-education/jai16-3-02>.
- [52] van Lehn K. The relative effectiveness of human tutoring, Intelligent Tutoring Systems, and other tutoring systems. *Educ Psychol* 2011;46(4):197–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.611369>.
- [53] Wang Y, Gong S, Cao Y, Fan W. The power of affective pedagogical agent and self-explanation in computer-based learning. *Comput Educ* 2023;195:104723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104723>.
- [54] White MC, Bembenuity H. Not all avoidance help seekers are created equal. *Sage Open* 2013;3(2):215824401348491. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244013484916>.
- [55] Wilkins JLM. Mathematics and science self-concept: an international investigation. *J Exp Educ* 2004;72(4):331–46. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JEXE.72.4.331-346>.
- [56] Wood D. Comments on "learning with ICT: new perspectives on help seeking and information searching. *Comput Educ* 2009;53(4):1048–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.07.002>.
- [57] Wood H, Wood D. Help seeking, learning and contingent tutoring. *Comput Educ* 1999;33(2–3):153–69. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1315\(99\)00030-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1315(99)00030-5).
- [58] Yang F, Stefaniak J. A systematic review of studies exploring help-seeking strategies in online learning environments. *Online Learning* 2023;27(1):107–26. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ej1382711>.
- [59] Zech F. *Grundkurs Mathematikdidaktik: theoretische und praktische anleitungen für das Lehren und Lernen von Mathematik*. 10. Auflage. Beltz. 2002.
- [60] Voermanek J, Schulz A. Which promotes learning success and acceptance better? Experimental comparison between an intelligent and a passive online learning environment. In: *INTED2023 Proceedings*. IATED; 2023. p. 809–19.